

BASIC METHODS OF TEACHING ENGLISH**Kochkarova Gulnoza Shavkiddin kyzy****Mamatkulova Gulandon Rustamjon kyzy****Scientific adviser: Gasanova Nasiba Shavkievna****Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages**

Annotation: The study of foreign languages in modern society has become an inseparable component of the training of specialists at all levels. The article undertakes a brief review of private methods of teaching foreign language communicative competence of students.

Keywords: Intensive methodology, foreign languages, foreign language communicative competence, textbook in English.

The beginning of the XXI century is characterized by an intensive process of introducing new information and communication technologies in foreign language teaching, creating new and innovative forms of education and training. Mobile foreign language teaching is a form of organization and control of the learning process based on the use of mobile communication devices, in which students in any place and at any time can shape and improve language skills, develop oral skills, to form the socio cultural and intercultural competence in order to use a foreign language as a means of communication in the social and domestic and professional spheres.

The term “mobile learning” is inextricably linked with the concept of “distance education”. This concept should be described as a form of learning in which the interaction between teachers and students and between students is carried out at a distance and involves all the typical components of the educational process. Depending on the means of implementation of distance learning, the latter can be divided into types: a) correspondence model of distance learning, based on the use of printed materials in hard-copy form; b) multimedia model, based on the study of printed, multimedia, video, audio materials, local computer programs; c) tele-education, based on the establishment of communication between teacher and students using TV systems (audio teleconferencing, videoconferencing, TV broadcast); d) Web-based training, carried out through a variety of communication and presentation of educational content suggested by Internet (access to Web resources, interactive multimedia), e) intellectual model of learning, including interactive multimedia,

access to Internet resources, computer communication between all participants of the educational process. It is obvious that mobile learning is the latest form - intellectual model - of the distance learning.

In practice, mobile learning is implemented by mobile technologies - mobile means of communication between people or obtaining instant access to relevant information. In foreign language teaching you may use the following mobile technologies: e-mail, blogging technology, wiki technology, podcasts, web forum, linguistic corpus, electronic dictionaries, reference Internet resources, tools of synchronous video Internet communication and navigators. Didactic functions are interpreted as representations of mobile technologies. Within the framework of different courses the same mobile technologies with their inherent properties and relevant didactic functions will represent different methodological functions within the discipline. Accordingly, methodical functions within foreign language teaching will be the methodical abilities of these technologies in the development of oral skills and language skills as well as the formation of students' socio-cultural and intercultural competences.

Let us briefly examine each of the technologies and denote types of performance or aspects of the language being developed on its basis.

A) E-mail or electronic mail group - Internet service for the exchange of written communications between users. On the basis of E-mail, this can be organized by telecommunication projects based on information exchange among participants. Methodological potential of e-mail and e-mail group was covered in dissertations. As a result, techniques have been developed for implementation of language telecommunication projects aimed at the development of writing skills of pupils and students, as well as the formation of their socio-cultural and intercultural competences.

B) Blog technology is a modern Internet technology that allows users to submit information on the page in multimedia format in the form of a diary or journal, as well as to comment on reports of users.

C) Wiki technology - one of the modern Internet technologies, enabling one person or group of persons located an indefinite (and unlimited) distance from each other to work on a common written (multimedia) document.

D) Podcasts – modern Internet technology, on the basis of which you can discover, listen, browse featured podcasts, and record and host your personal podcast. In the Internet there are a large number of academic and nonacademic (authentic) podcasts services that can be used for the development of students' listening skills. There are also services that allow users to post podcasts and arrange discussion of shared network podcasts in micro-blog or forum. The scientific literature lacks for methodological papers on the use of podcasts in the development of students' verbal skills. Thus, we can conclude that on the basis of podcasts service it is possible to develop oral and listening skills, as well as social competence of students.

E) Web Forum - section of the site, developed for network users to discuss any issue. The analysis of this study and other studies leads to the conclusion that based on a web forum we can develop writing and reading skills, as well as social competence components. However, we must note that a web forum gave out a bit after the development of blog technology that has additional technological capabilities.

G) Electronic dictionaries. On the basis of electronic dictionaries we can organize students' research (during reading), develop their cognitive activity, develop skills of cooperative learning and develop students' abilities for autonomous learning. Electronic dictionaries are used to develop students' lexical skills and to form their competence at translation.

I) Informational and reference network resources are available for all users of mobile devices through mobile applications of the Internet browsers. The informational and reference network resources include encyclopedias, directories, online media, virtual tours of museums, galleries, theaters, cities, etc. Informational and reference resources have the following common didactic properties: accessibility, multimedia, hypertext structure. This allows us to organize students' research work, to develop their cognitive activity, to develop skills of cooperative learning and abilities for autonomous learning.

Methodological papers on the use of network reference resources in foreign language teaching testify that on its basis we can develop a whole range of productive and receptive language skills, as well as develop aspects of socio-cultural and intercultural competence.

Analysis of studies dedicated to the use of the above mentioned technologies

in foreign language teaching testifies that on their basis we can develop productive (speaking and writing) and receptive (listening and reading) types of speech activity, develop students' language skills (grammatical and lexical) and their socio cultural and intercultural competence. This level of language proficiency is characterized by understanding of general content of professional texts, fast and spontaneous speech, ability to produce clear, detailed reports on professional issues, express original views on the basic problem of the text, revealing the advantages and disadvantages of various options.

In conclusion it should be noted that regular use of mobile technologies in foreign language teaching will facilitate the development of the aspects of communicative competence.

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